

Determinants of Adolescents Well Being

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Well-being is a dynamic concept that includes subjective, social, and psychological dimensions as well as health-related behaviors. Adolescents form two-thirds of our population, this is a unique group of people with special needs. The study aims to identify the lifestyle and behavioral patterns of this group and subsequently come up with issues that require special attention. The Competitive environment in every field has propelled maladjustment in different spheres of life such as home, social, health, emotion and educational problems. In order to address adolescents' psychological issues, it becomes everyone's responsibility to give assistance to protect the future generation.

Keywords: Emotional Changes, Mental Well Being, Risk Behavior, Social Protection.

Introduction

Adolescents is one of the most fascinating and complex transitions in the life span. It is a time of tremendous growth and potential. Adolescents are viewed as the leaders of tomorrow which are featured by rapid psychological changes, physiological changes and psycho social maturation. They experience different mode of world in a complex manner than their elders, they extend their relationship except their family and take things very seriously what their peers and outside world says. Gordon-Larsen, McMurray, and Popkin (2000) discussed about rapid changes in adolescents physically and emotionally as well as changes socially (like attending outdoor events, picnics, parties with friends and colleagues) these can pose new situations like indulging in drugs/alcohol use or sexual relationships.

Adolescents have to cope with many challenges such as hormonal fluctuations, higher achievement expectations, changes in school structure, expanded peer relations and influence, pressures from dating and emergent sexuality. (Shantz, 1987) expressed image of adolescence is intensely moodiness and always preoccupied with the self has flooded both professionally and place their perspectives on their developmental period. The families and parents are the most important support system for teens. The inconsistent usage of terms such as ego, identity, existential self, confusion, self-image and self-worth have enlarged Rosenberg (2015) during this time. Body dissatisfaction is highly prominent among adolescents and is related as a risk factor for decreasing psychological well-being, following lower self-esteem, obesity, eating disorder, dieting behaviors, and depression. Well-being means able to think rationally having good self-esteem and enjoying a feeling of comfort, when an individual is able to solve all sorts of problem, emotionally stable and have creativity in every field. The well-being of adolescents related both to individual and contextual factors. Mental and physical well-being in adolescent period is depend on the environment in which teens grow and develop explained by (Diener, 1994, 2000).

Literature Review

Coleman (2011) shared his view that adolescents have a poor reputation of getting along with their families. Parents faces serious problems when they have different opinion, ideas, and rules from their young adults and their adjustment with their family is really challenging. Here, parents understanding among spouse, techniques, sternness and patients play great role in handling adolescents.

Stages of Adolescents

The aim of adolescent stages is to move toward a more mature sense of self and determination. Young adults should learn how to initiate and sustain healthy relationships, to understand their abstract ideas, develop satisfaction and good behavior. World Health Organization (n.d.) studied development of adolescent commencing at 11 years and continuing till 19 years of age. These development were divided into early adolescents, middle adolescents and late adolescent stages respectively. The development invaded physical cognitive development as well as emotional development in an adolescent's life.

Physical Change: While undergoing physical change an adolescent gains body mass weight and height increase, and hormonal changes result in body hair growth, and development of reproductive changes in either gender. Also this creates physical awareness and attraction for opposite gender. Middle adolescents sets in between ages between 14 to 18 where it slows down for family but for male adolescents it continues unabated till around 19 to 21 years. So the adolescent's physical growth rate is different for both genders with girls maturing earlier physically than the males.

Cognitive Development: The thought process development in adolescents also matures and variants into capacity for abstract thought. The assimilations for knowledge, it's understanding and importance gains new dimensions in teenagers between ages 11 and 13 years. Also the ability for thinking or oral and immoral domains increases. This increase in the capacity for abstract thought capacity containers increasing as teen navigates through middle adolescents life stage as found by (Campbell, 1990). They are more interested in setting their goals based on moral reasoning, by introspecting their emotions and attained experiences. Adolescents exhibit concern towards future while being interested in moral reasoning. During teenage, adolescents are observed to be struggling with their sense of identity and have an uncomfortable sense of awkwardness about their bodily changes. Emotional changes are also exhibited by moodiness, trying to test boundaries and concerns of a greater privacy, but there exists normalcy towards societal emotional development (Perez, Espinoza, Ramos, Coronado, & Cortes, 2009). Towards approaching the stage of middle adolescent around 14 years of age teenagers become intensely self-involved and preoccupied. Their self- higher expectation leads them to reduced self-perception of themselves as they continually cope towards adjusting to their changing bodies and concerned with normalcy. The dependence on friends gradually increase as their distance from parents increase. There is also the evolution of love and passion feelings developing and romantic friendships are an important peer group affiliation. By the age of 19, as late adolescent stage sets in, teenagers now demonstrate a stronger sense of identity and show an emotional stability which is more independent in nature and has a higher degree of self-reliance within them stated by Hall and Valente (2007).

Different Life Changes Events of Adolescents

If teens will face issues relating to family life, like problems in relationship between family members, neglected some specific member of the family, family violence, death of any dear one, sexual abuse or school change, first love or break up, absence of parents or one parent only, psychiatric illness of anyone in families, health problem or emotional abuse, separation and divorce, than all these influence of deviant behavior, mood swings, aggression, increasing arguments. Adolescent behavior which is problem for them, for the family and for the society is rebellious behavior. The violent exhibition by teenagers, are warning signs of aggression and violence invading their life changes. This is depicted by brandishing weapons and playing with them. Obsessive addiction with violent videos games or viewing violent content while glorifying violence. Indulging in acts of bullying, threatening people and showing cruelty to pets. Also fantasizing acts of committing violence as a sense of self-gratification (Ali, 2015), they are confused about it as the adults. These are some of the behavior changes that are seen in adolescents and can be dealt with proper support.

Challenges of Turning into Adolescents

It is a very turbulent period which requires adjustment to self- change, and with changes in family and peer groups (Lerner, Bornstein, & Smith, 2003). So it becomes essential for the adolescents to learn positive adaptive behavior life skill to be successful and strike balance in life. Life skill will develop only when an adolescents will become positive, when he is balanced, enhanced his personality in various direction and it needs lots of preparation, planning (Boora, 2011).

Behavioral Problem: Behavioral problem (internalizing and externalizing). As Farrington, Jolliffe, Loeber, Stouthamer-Loeber, and Kalb (2001) reported that adolescents with externalizing behavior problem of conduct disorder are very likely to become delinquents during adolescent's criminals and violent individual during adulthood. Similarly adolescent with internalizing problem are expected more to grow up becoming anxious, shy, alienated and depressed individual as reported by APA in (1994).

Risk Behavior: Adolescents wish for excitement in novel ways which is in comprehensible to adults. While normal adolescent find difficult to understand. Well minded adolescents cope to find their excitement in sports, music, positive health and involving energy activities. But for experiment they drinking or smoking with friends adolescents resort to or indulge in thrilling activities may be dangerous. A young person is in greater danger if he/she indulges in these activities alone by themselves (Spraggins, 2009). While warnings from peers or older adolescents are taken on a serious note rather than heeding to warning from parents.

Residential crowding: Because of less living area (No. of people per room), loud interior and exterior noise are the reason of psychological distress studied by (Hinshaw & Kranz, 2009). Stinking air pollutants higher negativity affect, some toxins cause behavior disorder such as self-regulatory ability, aggression, and dysthymia. High rising houses is unfriendly to the psychological well-being, insufficient day light is reliably associated with increased depressive symptoms.

Lacking Compassion: Now a day's adolescents are prone to see violence or accidents in day today life, in news, in movies, in games from where they picks these habits of fighting, arguing, bullying, and starring. In movies criminals are so glamorized and fashionable that these young minds get so impressed that without knowing, they are going in the wrong path Halloran (1964) studied that surfeit of brutality, violence and sadism has made a profound impression of young people who are becoming more hostile, callous and insensitive.

Alienation: Alienation is as the disease of modern human being, who is estranged from herself, from her feelings, from her own love and from nature. Alienation from both inside and outside M. E. Stewart, Donaghey, Deary, and Ebmeier (2008) which develops as a response to the external environment as a defense mechanism against it. They feel threats for their feelings of isolation and loneliness and the belief that one is alone or insignificant which leads psychological disorder Marchand and Hock (2003) identified avoidance behavior of parents to be as significant predictors of adolescents internalizing behavior.

Illegal Behavior: Anderson and Dill (2000) studied violence, aggression and illegal behavior and the tendency to engage in activities that have the potential to be harmful or dangerous. Teen break plan and impulse control and they are not mature until age 25. Sometimes adolescents make decisions about potentially risky things to fit in with a group.

Cognitive Distortion: Cognitive Distortion is 'faulty thinking' faulty thinking pattern exist for many different reasons (McCrae & Costa, 2003). Purpose of cognitive distortion is to reject responsibility for their behavior, to disagree with their self-created negative consequences, continuously to behave in a specific manner, to avoid

facing painful emotions, to avoid changes. For adolescents it is very difficult to accept negative things easily because they are not mature enough to understand reality.

Environmental Effect on Adolescents

A healthy environment leads to a healthier population and a better quality of life in adolescents. Coping problem to well-being as faced by adolescents.

Psychological and emotional changes: Adolescents develop close relationships outside their own family, and with same aged friends and sometimes with older people than them, older friends sometimes are more dangerous. J.M. Twenge (2006) explained that adolescents like to spend time among their age group or with electronic device. This is how they feel important way of independence. These friendships evolve into learning as to how to mingle in their surroundings, and gaining a sense of well-defined identity which is different from their family although which is very lethal for them these days. Parents assume a lesser important role in their children's eyes. As adolescents become more independent, they want to try out new things, but often recognize in experience to fall back when things get difficult, for them and it changes their self-confidence in an immense way.

Romantic relationships: When adolescents will not get support, love from their family than these unsecured adolescents easily get involved in romantic relationship. Romantic relationships changed longer-term goals for an individual Furman and ShaVer (2003). Sometimes it becomes very serious, and in result in emotional turmoil. While physical changes are very awkward and embarrassing for adolescents, and they would feel inhibited at to ask questions about it from their family so they discuss outside and involve in all these traps.

Problems in School: Adolescents who are truant or drop out of school, are usually depressed and heavy hearted from home and frustrated at school. Shaw, Brady, and Davey (2011) said that bullying, emotional problems, incomplete homework, not able to understand what teachers are teaching will often affect interest in school. Excessive nagging from parents can prove to be counterproductive. Although examinations are important for a child, but they should not dominate in their life or cause of unhappiness. School climate is a complex construct like quality of interpersonal relationships between consisting of multiple components (Freiberg, 2005) like quality of interpersonal relations between student and teachers, expectation from students in academy.

Survival of Fittest: In today's world adolescents living in a cut throat competition in every sphere of life. The theory of "SURVIVAL OF THE FITTEST" relate to each and every step of the society. Adolescent are living in full anxiety and threaten atmosphere. The most important thing that an individual should be academically sound and have a place for oneself in the society. Chen and Marcus (2012) suggested that social problem is a major stressor when adolescents have behavior disorder and often experiences negative outcomes and their action mislead and displaying in reasoning about social issues.

Identity formation: The social experiences of adolescence have an influence on their identity formation. Mejia (2014) suggested that usage of drugs, cigarette, and pipe depends on peer pressure and confusion of life and expectations from all the side and various social problems. Disturbed adolescents were get attracted towards more in negative alternatives for the solution of social problems such as running away from the situation, having alcohol, prefer isolation only because they want to run away from their surrounding from themselves.

Stigma: Hinshaw and Kranz (2009) found that stigma affects an individual's (adolescents) sense of self-esteem and self-worth. This restrict an adolescent's ability to seek psychological and emotional support through disclosure to others. Although stigma can be directed at another person or generated by the decisions of others; it can also take the form of self-stigma when a person internalizes and accepts the stigmatizing attitudes of others toward themselves. This often result in a damaging effects on feelings of the individual's self-worth.

Allergies: Ecological change and rising of carbon dioxide level may increase the incidence of atmosphere allergies, food allergies which would have an impact on psychological health (Ali, 2015). Any sought of allergies have

higher rate of stress, anxiety, panic disorder, depression, social phobia and bipolar disorder. Even parents of such adolescents have also irritating behavior, stress and anxiety studied by Beggs and Walczyk (2008).

Table 1 - Dimensions of Adolescents Well-Being

Factors	Variables	Major Findings	Studies
Environmental Effects	Mental Illness, Stigma, identity formation, survival of fittest experimenting sex, alcohol, drugs, harming behaviour such as cutting	Violence, show-off, bullying, shyness, dissatisfaction, attitudinal problem, self-concept, risk behaviour, Allergies, disregard house rule or laws of society	(Beggs & Walczyk, 2008; Hall & Valente, 2007; Rosenberg, 2015; Shaw et al., 2011; Spraggins, 2009)
Life changing Events	Social protection, Risk behaviour, residential crowding, Cognitive distortion, problem in school, reluctant to get up early for school, Behavior Problem,	Family, peer group, achievement, stigma, Romantic relationship, friendship, risk- illegal behaviour, identity development, sign of distress or depression	(Anderson & Dill, 2000; Freiberg, 2005; Furman & ShaVer, 2003; Hinshaw & Kranz, 2009; Lerner et al., 2003; Shantz, 1987)
Stages of Adolescents	Physical changes	Tremendous physical growth, sexual interest, oil production in hair and skin, allergies	(Coleman, 2011; Gordon-Larsen et al., 2000; McCrae & Costa, 2003) Ali (2015).
	Social development	Sense of identity, feel awkward for their body, conflict with parents, feeling of love and passion, closeness with their age group, interest in privacy, moodiness, alienation	(Hall & Valente, 2007; Marchand & Hock, 2003; M. E. Stewart et al., 2008; Jean M Twenge, Baumeister, DeWall, Ciarocco, & Bartels, 2007)
	Cognitive development	Decision making, abstract thoughts, interest in present with limit thought for the future, examination of inner experience, moral reasoning	(Campbell, 1990; Diener, 1994, 2000; Farrington et al., 2001; Gordon-Larsen et al., 2000)
Psychological Effects	Motivation, self-concept, achievement, alienation, furious and faulty thinking, dysthymia, cognitive distortion, lacking compassion, self-consciousness	Depression, anxiety, eating disorder, conduct disorder, attention deficit, oppositional defiant disorder, borderline personality disorder, bipolar disorder, panic disorder	(Chen & Marcus, 2012; Garber & Hollon, 1991; Halloran, 1964; Lu, Gilmour, & Kao, 2001; Santos, Page, Cooper, Ribeiro, & Mota, 2009)

Source: Compilation by Author

Mental Illness: As an adolescents traverses through emotional, social and physical changes in their life, they may encounter psychologically turbulent environments. A possibility of resultant mental illness may occur. In

adolescents, this could derive in many forms, owing to widespread issues in behavioral and psychiatric problems. Examples of these psychological illness could range from attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, dysthymia, bipolar disorder, schizophrenia, suicide, and to even eating disorders. Studies have indicated that it is not limiting but can happen at the time of relocation from one environment to another example a city, school or changing of house (Santos et al., 2009).

Methodology

The scope of the study is limited to adolescent in the age group (12-18) living in urban setting and all of them attending school in the class 7 to 11 and living in their natural families. This is the scope and limited to the geographical confines of Northern India. The dimensions of environmental and life changing events were limited to psychological context. The study has following objectives

- How does environment impact adolescent stages towards?
- How role of life changing affecting adolescents?

This paper is aimed at exploring relationship of adolescents and to assess the extent to which these strategies would benefit them. Paper is exploratory in nature and is built upon the thorough review of past literature. Data for this study were drawn from an analysis of documents sources, consisting primarily of research papers from reputed journals and from thesis.

Hypothesis

H₁: Life changing events have an impact on stages of adolescents

H₂: Environmental effects have an impact on stages of adolescents

H₃: Life stages have an impact on stages of adolescents

Figure 1 - Theoretical Model

Discussion

Strategies for Adolescents Well-Being

Talking about Values: Home is somewhere where an individual feels safe, and protected, cared for and taken seriously (Security Safety Today, n.d.). A healthy lifestyle in home is essential for adolescents. Parents should realize that what adolescents are absorbing in home, it is determining that these young adults see world in the same way, live their life with the same way, with same ideas, and with the same fundamentals either they are positive and negative. While gaining independence, adolescents continually learn behavioral skills from their friends, relative, associates and their parents. Parents should refrain from violence if they don't want their

children to be violent. Also similarly if kindness is a virtue which needs to be inculcated in adolescents, they ought to be treated with kindness.

Homework: Homework is an important practice and mental disposition of a teenager's regarding their academic performance and educational development. Parents should be involved with their children homework regularly, they need structure, and this routine will develop their cognitive skills or abilities suggested by (Shaw et al., 2011). In this way they will learn good study skills and habits, time management.

Mutual support: Parents are required to be satisfied in their relation and have respect towards their basic values and rules. Also support each other in applying them. Parents will not get respect from their teenager when they will always discouragement them and are dejected with each other. This usually leads to constant trouble in their life.

Shared same interests. Fathers and sons often connect themselves over sports; mothers and daughters over gossip or watch movies together. The aim is that family should have common interests that can spent time with each other qualitatively and discuss any issue peacefully. So their children will feel more comfortable and open relationship about different things.

Try to understand reason of their bitterness and anger. Adolescent's anger is only a feeling or an emotion not a behavior. If our adolescent are sad, anxious or depressed than we should know reason behind it, it can be because of incompetency, prejudice because of sarcasm, with drawl, insufficiency, or may be repress feeling maybe he want a good listener or healthy relationship but it should be without judgment.

Easy Listening. If a teenager have faith in their parents, that they are good listener and comfortable couple studied by S. H. Stewart and Devine (2000). This helps them in enhancing their performance in every field. Enhancement of emotional and mental well-being may lead not only to reduction in behavior disorder (conduct disorder and oppositional defiant disorder) in adolescents but also improve one's overall performance as well as other functioning across multiple domains of life. Parents should tell their own stories, to identify their hopes and goals treatment, and for feeling valued and understood by adolescents.

Managing disagreements. Involvement of adolescents towards making family rules should be encouraged. If a teenager observes that the family rule is useful for their younger siblings, they may have still abide by the family rules, even while being reluctant to discuss rules for themselves (Sallis et al., 2006). If left to isolation, i.e., once parents stop reacting to them, they develop the most annoying habit of self-destruction.

Don't use physical (corporal) punishment. Many times people still infrequently smack younger children which reinforce the action that violence is a permissible act to handle few situations. This instill in adolescents that violence is acceptable and they grow as adults with this internalization (Study on Child Abuse, 2007).

Mental Well-Being. The Mental wellbeing can produce better by focusing on the fundamentals of our family and culture. It is not just that we are eating, exercising and not getting stressed, but what is beneath that plays role is the real change. It is our past experience, knowledge, awareness that affect the decisions we make, the life choices and how we respond to situations we experience stated by Lu et al. (2001).

Problems of Adjustment

Create a Structured Environment: Ajzen (1991) stated that a structured, healthy lifestyle will not only benefit a child involve sleep but their entire family environment. Physical activity like exercise, sleep, plays a key role in reducing negative thinking and affective adolescent's behavior in their well-being, those who are habitual of

physical activity lessen stress and lower levels of depression and good in mental health and well-being (Floyd et al., 2011).

Adequate Parenting: It requires the action of suitable and right support and nurturing, the encouragement to develop independence. It should be with clear boundaries and conditional reinforcement (praise or punishment) for behavior.

Parents should be Eustress: Parents should manage their stress and create a support network. Find other adults such as your spouse, teachers, and coaches to work together. Family is a major socializing group and important in determining an adolescent’s motivation to achieve successful life.

Daily Routine: Eat a healthy diet. Well-nourished and balanced diet will help in reducing anxiety, depression and abnormal behavior in teens. Reduce junk food which is the major cause of abnormal behavior and for hormonal disorder.

Empathy: Empathy means putting oneself in another person’s character or situation (Jean M Twenge et al., 2007). Empathy means to understand relation regarding pro social behavior which is defined as action to help an individual. Parenting behavior developed self-control, compliance, pro social behavior in adolescent. It is to decrease personal distress of the person at the time of help.

Table 2 - Strategies Employed for Adolescents Well-Being

Component of Behavioral Treatment	Description	Studies
Focus on Positive	Physical activity, surrounded by greenery	
Goal setting	Setting realistic for studies, set an example, structured environment	(Ajzen, 1991; Floyd et al., 2011)
Parental involvement	Parental support is vital for behavior treatment program, good listener	(Security Safety Today, n.d.; S. H. Stewart & Devine, 2000)
Education	Nutritional education, daily routine, homework, mutual support, social and personal values	(Shaw et al., 2011)
Mutual Support	Help in all homework, projects, adequate parenting, parent should manage their stress	(Lu et al., 2001)
Safety concerns	Safety concerns inside and outside	
Punishment avoidance	Don't use physical (corporal) punishment, manage disagreement	(Sallis et al., 2006; Study on Child Abuse, 2007)
Empathy	Personal distress, perspective taking, self-control	(Jean M Twenge et al., 2007)
Eustress	Positive response, productivity, success, positive thinking	(Deb, Strodl, & Sun, 2015)

Sources: Compilation by Author

Social Protection: Adolescence is an unpredictable period that can put them in conflict, enjoying risk in their life and always have problem with the law and with their health. Garber and Hollon (1991) framed to social protection programmes for adolescents which will improve teen’s health, their educational achievement and

lessen the chance of danger, different types of abuses and exploitation. While a small proportion of adolescents develop bad habits of drug abuse, violent behaviour and criminality that harmful for them only.

Conclusion

Adolescents are confronted with unique challenges towards achieving good psychological health during their teenage years. They need to develop their own sense of individual identity, their own world-views and values in life. It is important for them that they should not isolate themselves either physically socially or environmentally i.e., within the confines of solitary music or virtual world. Adolescents needs include distinct recognition and treatment a distinct as an important segment of our population. Families of teenagers can prove to be a great source to help Nasar, Holloman, and Abdulkarim (2015) in studying physiological effects like inadequate sleep, depression and smoking lead adolescents to unhealthy behavior. This being significant as it often necessitates young people towards developing their own identity. Adolescent relationships with their family and friends will undergo dramatic changes. Parents incline their children for a long term decisions e.g. Values and morals and career choices and their friends influence for short-term choices such as appearance, interest. They will be emotionally strong and positive, will have an inclination to be in a good mental state and have healthy adjustment with their environment. Studies have reported that high parental attachment likely to reduce emotional problem among adolescents (Murray & Greenberg, 2000).

Parents have to adopt a flexible attitude in dealing with adolescent's relationship. This may make them feel a considerable strain themselves. Parents have a pivotal role to play towards contributing to the emotional, spiritual and physical health of an adolescents. They also share responsibility to provide guidance, direction according to their interest, firmness and establish proper domain in understanding and value of family. When unconditional love is there and communication is open in the family members, than parents have to be reasonable and loving in dealing with the mistakes and failures of their teens. By the time an adolescents reaches the later part of his teen years. They are already entrenched and reinforced establishing patterns of self-determination. Thus they would learn to make their own decisions. It is concluded that good environment parenting is one of the reasons for good, stable, healthy behavior.

Direction for Future Research: For future work in the area, it is important to focus on association of life changing events with psychological effects and different of demographic, divorcees, adults. How to understand their emotional and physical problems and their association. Research should also be directed among different types of environmental (urban and rural) settings. Also, it may study adolescents from metropolitan and cosmopolitan culture.

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